

CFD Analysis of Solar Air Heater having Ribs - A Critical Review

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Abstract: Solar energy is radiation from the sun that can produce heat, cause chemical processes, or generate electricity. The entire amount of solar energy that reaches the Earth is far greater than the energy needs of the world today and in the future. The amount of solar energy that the Earth receives each day is around 200,000 times greater than the total amount of electricity that is generated around the world in a day. This means that solar energy has a huge potential. Solar cells are capable of converting solar light directly into electricity. When light hits the junction between a metal and a semiconductor (like silicon) or the junction between two separate semiconductors, a modest electric potential is produced in these types of cells. The current study work examines the thermal performance of solar air heaters and how it might be improved through the use of artificial roughness. The study found that artificial roughness definitely enhances the efficacy of solar air heaters.

Keywords: Solar Energy, Solar Radiation, Solar Cells, Solar Air Heaters, Artificial Roughness

I. Introduction

Solar energy is radiation from the sun that can produce heat, cause chemical processes, or generate electricity. The entire amount of solar energy that reaches the Earth is far greater than the energy needs of the world today and in the future. This widely available source has the ability to meet all future energy requirements if it is properly utilised. Solar energy is anticipated to become a more appealing renewable energy source in the 21st century due to its limitless supply and its lack of pollution. This is in stark contrast to fossil fuels such as coal, petroleum, and natural gas, which are limited in availability.

The Sun is a very strong source of energy, and sunlight is the biggest source of energy that reaches the Earth. However, the amount of sunlight that reaches the surface of the Earth is rather modest. The main reason for this is the vast radial dispersion of radiation that is emitted by the Sun, which is located far away. Earth's atmosphere and clouds absorb or scatter up to 54 percent of the sunlight that reaches them, which results in a relatively small additional loss of sunlight. The sunlight that reaches the earth is made up of almost 50 percent visible light, 45 percent infrared radiation, and lower amounts of ultraviolet and other types of electromagnetic radiation..

Fig. 1 Reflection and absorption of solar energy (<https://www.britannica.com/science/solar-energy>)

The amount of solar energy that the Earth receives each day is around 200,000 times greater than the total amount of electricity that is generated around the world in a day. This means that solar energy has a huge potential. Sadly, even though solar energy is free, the high costs of collecting, converting, and storing it still prevent it from being used in many locations. Solar radiation can be transformed into either thermal energy (heat) or electrical energy, but the former is easier to do.

Flat-plate collectors are one of the most frequent devices used to catch solar energy and transform it into thermal energy. They are utilised for solar heating applications. These collectors must have a vast surface area since the intensity of solar radiation at the surface of the Earth is very low. A collector must have a surface area of approximately 40 square meters (430 square feet) in order to collect enough energy to meet the energy needs of one person, even in sunny areas of the world's temperate zones.

The most common type of flat-plate collector is made out of a blackened metal plate that is coated with one or two sheets of glass. The sunlight that falls on the plate heats it up. The heat is subsequently transmitted to air or water, which are called carrier fluids, that flow past the rear of the plate. The heat can be used directly, or it can be transferred to another material for storage. Solar water heaters and home heating systems often use flat-plate collectors. Insulated tanks are often used to hold the water that is heated during sunny hours. This water can then be used to retain heat for usage at night or on overcast days. This type of system can offer hot water to a residence by drawing it from the storage tank, or it can provide space heating by circulating warmed water through tubes in the ceilings and floors. Flat-plate collectors usually heat carrier fluids to temperatures between 66 and 93 °C (150 and 200 °F). Depending on the design of the collector, the efficiency of such collectors (that is, the percentage of energy that they convert into usable energy) can be anywhere from 20 to 80 percent.

Solar ponds, which are lakes of saline water that are meant to gather and store solar energy, are another way to convert thermal energy. The heat that is taken from these ponds can be utilised to produce chemicals, food, textiles, and other industrial products. It can also be used to heat greenhouses, swimming pools, and cattle facilities. Solar ponds are occasionally used to generate power by means of the organic Rankine cycle engine, which is a relatively efficient and inexpensive way to convert solar energy. This method is especially beneficial in remote places. Solar ponds are typically only found in warm rural settings, and they are somewhat costly to install and maintain.

Solar air heating is a solar thermal method that uses an absorbing media to catch energy from the sun, known as insolation, and then uses that energy to heat air. Solar air heating is a renewable energy technique that is used to heat or condition air for buildings or process heat applications. It is usually the most affordable option among all solar technologies, particularly in commercial and industrial settings. It also tackles the highest consumption of building energy in heating climates, which is space heating and industrial process heating.

Solar air heat technology can be used in a range of applications to reduce the carbon footprint that comes from using conventional heat sources, such as fossil fuels, to offer a sustainable way to produce thermal energy. Solar air heat devices can be used for applications such as space heating, extending the greenhouse season, pre-heating ventilation makeup air, and process heating. Solar co-generation is a field that combines solar thermal technologies with photovoltaics (PV) in order to enhance the efficiency of the system. This is accomplished by cooling the PV panels to improve their electrical performance while concurrently warming air for space heating.

II. Literature Survey

Agarwal, A. & al. (2024) Solar air heaters are typically used for drying food or heating air. The solar air heater consists of the collection body, duct, absorber glass surface, air intake, and air exit tube. In the current study, the solar collector model is created using Creo parametric design software and then imported into ANSYS design modeller. The ANSYS CFX simulation package is used to perform thermal study of the solar air dryer at various Reynolds numbers. V-shaped artificial roughness is added to the upper absorber plate in order to improve heat transfer. The angles of the V-shaped artificial roughness that were taken into account for the analysis are 60° , 90° , and 120° . The thermal study provides the heat transfer coefficient (HTC) value, pressure drop, and thermo hydraulic performance parameter for various V-shaped artificial roughness profiles. The results of the CFD simulation have demonstrated that adding ribs to the design of the solar collector improves its heat transfer rate and THPF (thermo-hydraulic performance factor). Across all Reynolds numbers, the V-shaped ribs with a rib angle of 60° have demonstrated better thermal-hydraulic performance than those with rib angles of 90° and 120° .

According to Sharma, S. L et al. (2024), the Solar Air Heater (SAH) is an important technology for transforming solar radiation into heat applications. This research aims to improve the performance of SAH by making changes to the

absorber surface, namely by adding ribs to create artificial roughness. A two-dimensional computational fluid dynamics (CFD) investigation examines how C-shape, reverse C-shape, and reverse R-shape ribs affect thermal and hydraulic performance in the SAH channel. The RNG (k- ϵ) turbulence model is used for numerical simulation, and the accuracy of the model is confirmed by comparing it to established correlations and results from the literature. The numerical study consists of the design and modelling of the SAH utilising a constant pitch ratio (P/e) of 14.285 and a height ratio (e/D) of 0.021. The current study examined Reynolds numbers (Re) ranging from 4000 to 18000. The current rib geometries greatly improve heat transfer and fluid mixing, resulting in a major increase in the Nusselt number (Nu) and friction factor (f) by 2.5 to 3.3 times and 2.8 to 5.05 times, respectively, compared to a smooth duct SAH. The C-shape rib arrangement has the highest Thermohydraulic Performance Factor (THPF) of about 2.0078 for a Re of 4000, outperforming both the reverse C-shape and reverse R-shape ribs.

According to Rajiv Saxena et al. (2023), the solar air heater (SAH) is a solar energy gathering device that is commonly used for a variety of purposes, including drying agricultural products, heating rooms, seasoning timber, and curing industrial items. SAH is the most affordable option when it comes to devices that collect solar energy. Using a surface that has been intentionally roughened is one excellent way to improve heat transfer to the fluid that is flowing through the duct of a SAH. For the last forty years, researchers have been investigating the use of artificial roughness in SAHs. This study gives a detailed summary of the many kinds of roughness geometry that can be used to create artificial roughness in SAHs in order to enhance their efficiency. The study examines different rib designs and how well they transfer heat. It proposes that using a mix of different rib shapes can enhance the thermal performance of SAH.

According to Hedau et al. (2023), an air heater that is powered by sunlight has a slower rate of heat transfer due to the creation of a thinner layer of heat at the surface of the absorbing plate. Furthermore, the use of artificial roughness increases the amplification of turbulence across the outermost region of the absorbent plate, which causes the heat boundary layer to split and fracture. A 3-D simulation is conducted to study heat transmission and frictional properties in a dual-pass air heating system that is powered by sunlight. The simulation is centred on the application of semicircular tubing and a perforated baffle that has simulated roughness. This numerical analysis is performed using a variety of variables: tube amplitude fractions (a/H) that range from 0.2 to 0.5, baffle altitude proportions (e/H) that range from 0.4 to 0.8, surface area proportions (β) that range from 13% to 30%, and Reynolds amounts (Re) that range from 3000 to 19000. The laboratory assessment rig is designed to confirm the accuracy of numerical results for specific parameters. These parameters include an e/H ratio of 0.4, a 30% open area percentage, an a/H ratio of 0.3, and a Reynolds value that can range from 3000 to 15000. The numerical results show a strong agreement with the data from the experiment, with a frictional factor (fr) of 5.28%. The highest Nusselt number observed is 274.29, which occurs at a Reynolds number of 19,000 and an e/H ratio of 0.8. On the other hand, the largest

friction issue that was found was 0.6290. This occurred at a Reynolds amount of 3000 and an e/H ratio of 0.8. The measurements were taken under consistent conditions, with a 30% open area proportion and an a/H number of 0.3. The highest THPP value that was measured within the specified range is 2.51. The value was measured at a Reynolds amount of 3000, a β coefficient of 30%, an e/H ratio of 0.4, and an a/H ratio of 0.3. In addition, simulation data has been used to establish mathematical relationships between the Nusselt value and the friction factor. These correlations take into account parameters like as a/H , e/H , and Reynolds number. According to Fadala et al. (2023), SAHs are most frequent and economically efficient systems of solar energy. A number of researchers have conducted a variety of experimental and analytical studies on solar heaters with SAH roughness. These studies involve the collecting of solar radiation by an absorbent plate and the subsequent transfer of heat to the air. This work provides a thorough examination of the synthetic roughness components that disrupt the laminar airflow over the outer surface of the absorbent plate. The goal is to improve the absorption of heat during the transfer process in the conduit of the solar airflow heater. This example examines how different artificial surface flaws affect both efficiency and heat transmission. The studies presented on this page demonstrate the connection between the form and makeup of artificial surface flaws and their various characteristics, ultimately leading to an increase in the effectiveness of SAH.

A. Kumar In their study, et al. (2023) conducted an evaluation of the performance of SAHs. The heaters have winglet-shaped roughness components that are attached to the outermost plate. The inquiry employed the liquid crystal measurement of temperature (LCT) method to assess the enhancement of heat transfer in the collector region and the changes in pressure characteristics throughout the extended test area. When comparing a roughened surface to a smooth surface under similar flow conditions, the key parameters of the roughened surface have a direct impact on the quantity of heat transferred, augmentation values, and pressure characteristics. The non-dimensional variables of the texture element were assessed by taking into account the following: P/e values that ranged from 5 to 12, attack angles (α) that ranged from 30° to 75° , W/w values that ranged from 3 to 7, and Reynolds numbers (Re) that ranged from 3000 to 22,000. The evaluation also considered how the varying flow rates of the air mass (m) affected the results. The parametric setting values were studied, and their effects on the Nusselt percentage, friction variable, and pressure reduction characteristics over the specified test segment were analysed. As a result, the enhanced value of its optimal state due to the rough surface has been calculated in comparison to that of the one that is smooth. However, when the conditions are the same, the pressure drop over the test portion is greater than the pressure drop over the seamless portion.

Kushagra Saurabh and his colleagues (2022) conducted a computer examination of a solar-powered heating and cooling system (SAH) that was outfitted with artificial unevenness in the form of dual concave ribs. A solar-powered air heating system is a device that uses rays from the sun to create heat through a heat exchanger. A common problem with smoother solar-powered air heaters is that they waste energy by transferring heat from the plate that collects heat to the air around it. A synthetic surface with two concave ribs is

used to improve the speed at which heat is transmitted. The geometric variables chosen for examination are e/D , P/e , and arc radius in relation to roughness (r/e). The study investigates how these elements affect the transmission of heat, the friction variable, and the THPP at five different levels of Re . The widely accessible CFD program Ansys Fluent is used in this experiment. The highest value of THPP that was determined during the examination of the set of parameters is 1.725. The Nusselt number is directly related to the Reynolds number, while the friction ratio is inversely related to the Reynolds number. However, when the r/e increases, both the Nusselt amount and the friction factor drop.

According to Usman Allauddin et al. (2022), SAHs are devices that efficiently convert energy from the sun into heat, making them suitable for a wide range of practical uses. CFD can improve the design and performance of solar-fueled air heating systems, which can increase their thermal efficiency. A thorough quantitative analysis is carried out to examine the unique features of fluid transfer and circulation in a solar-powered air heating system that has been improved with unique V-shaped ribs arranged in a staggered pattern. The study used numerical simulations with the $k-\epsilon$, RNG turbulent conditions model to analyse three-dimensional steady-state settings. The results that were obtained showed a significant level of agreement with the empirical data. The effect of rib spacing was studied by changing $P:e$ between 6 and 14 while adjusting Re from 4000 to 14,000. It was observed that the solar-powered air heater with ribbed sides had a considerable improvement in thermal efficiency. It was also shown that changing the $P:e$ ratio to a value between 6 and 10 increases the Nu for all of the Reynolds numbers (Re) that were investigated. A $P:e$ proportion of 10 at Re of 12,000 was estimated to have an expected increase of about 72.6% in Nu augmentation. It has been shown that increasing the $P:e$ ratio between 10 and 14 causes a drop in the Nu amount for all Reynolds levels that were tested.

According to Alaskari M et al. (2022), applying artificial roughness to a Solar Air Heater (SAH) absorber plate is a common method for improving its overall thermal efficiency (η_t-th). This research investigates how the geometrical parameters of V-down ribs, which are mounted below the corrugated absorbing plate of a SAH, affect the η_t-th . The effects of important roughness parameters, such as relative pitch p/e (6–12), relative height e/D (0.019–0.043), angles of attack α ($30-75^\circ$), and Re (1000–20,000), were studied in real weather situations. Using a computer model for conjugate heat transfer that was developed in-house, the SAH η_t-th roughened by V-down ribs was projected. Under the steady-state parameters of $Re = 20,000$, solar irradiance $G = 1000$ W/m^2 , $p/e = 8$, $e/D = 0.043$, and $\alpha = 60$, the maximal SAH η_t-th was projected to be 78.8%. The outcome was a 15.7% increase in efficiency when compared to the default smooth surface. The η_t-th of the roughened SAH with single- and double-glass coverings were 17.7 and 20.1%, respectively, under actual weather circumstances. These values were greater than those of the smooth SAH.

Shubham Agrawal et al. (2019) have demonstrated that the application of artificial roughness on the underside of the absorber plate in a solar air heater duct is a widely utilised method for repairing heat transfer with a moderate increase in the friction factor. In order to optimise the roughened surfaces, it is essential to carefully consider the design of the

roughness form and arrangement. This article examines the heat transmission and friction characteristics of solar air heaters that have been intentionally roughened and have varying roughness geometries. The article provides the official report on the current progress of the topic, reviews the previous advances, and sheds light on the future directions. An effort has been made to compare the performance of solar air heaters with different types of roughness geometries, using correlations that have been suggested in the literature. The performance of various roughness geometries is assessed by evaluating thermal efficiency, the thermal efficiency improvement factor (TEIF), thermo-hydraulic efficiency, effective efficiency, and exergetic efficiency performance parameters.

Sudhir Kumar et al. (2020) conducted a computational investigation using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) software to examine the impact of roughness on heat transfer and fluid friction in a solar air heater. The study focused on a new geometry of roughness in the sinusoidal form, and the results obtained were compared with experimental results. The simulated findings for the smooth solar air heater are compared with the Dittus-Boelter equation for heat transfer and the Blasius equation for fluid friction. The difference between the simulated results is determined to be 7.55% and 16.91%, respectively. To confirm the results of the simulation, an experimental test rig was built and trials were conducted using the same set of parameters as were used in the simulation. The experimental results show that the roughened absorber plate with a sinusoidal rib has a heat transfer variance of 9% from the simulated values and a fluid friction deviation of 4%. The best value of thermohydraulic performance (THP) is 2.05, which occurs when the roughness pitch (P) is 10 mm and the Reynolds number (Re) is 4000. At this point, the enhancement ratio of Nusselt number (Nur/Nus) and friction factor (fr/fs) are 2.48 and 1.76, respectively. The experimental value of THP is determined to be within 6.77% of the value indicated by CFD analysis. The results are also compared with the triangular and square ribs, and it was discovered that the optimal THP of the proposed rib is 20.06% and 33.31% greater.

Walid Rouissi et al. (2021) This research focusses on a numerical parametric optimisation study of a new configuration for a Solar Flat Air Collector (SFAC). The CFD numerical parametric study looks at different SFAC structures inside the air cavity, both with and without obstacles. The obstacles are spherical, cubic, cylindrical, and pyramidal. The research improves the most practical structure and arrangement that allow for the expansion of the heat-transfer surface and the creation of a uniform flow in order to produce turbulence zones within the SFAC air cavity. The results indicate that the thermal performance of the cubic form is similar to that of the spherical barriers. A new set of simulations was conducted to assess how well the cubic shape baffles worked at three different orientation angles: 0° , 22.5° , and 45° . Every configuration has three different ways to be arranged, and the relative roughness pitch (b/a) can be 2, 4, or 6. The simulation study's findings indicated that the relative roughness pitch, the Reynolds number, and the angle of orientation all had an effect on the SFAC's performance and operation. The results of the simulations demonstrated that the combination of a 45° orientation and a roughness

pitch of $b/a = 2$ improves the SFAC thermal performance, which can reach up to 85%.

M. Al-Damook et al. (2019) This paper looks into how flow configurations affect the thermal performance of a solar heater system. Recycled aluminium cans (RAC) have been used as turbulators in a double pass single duct solar air collector. Three designs are modelled using the CFD program of COMSOL Multiphysics V5.3a: co-current (model A), counter-current (model B), and U-shape (model C). The U-shape design has a thermal performance that is 5.4% and 6.5% better than the cocurrent and counter-current flow models, respectively, according to the numerical data. An outdoor experiment is conducted based on the numerical modelling of flow configurations. The experimental setting is tested using three different configurations of model C: the solar air heater (SAH) without RAC model C-I (simple model), the SAH with in-line RAC layout (model C-II), and the SAH with staggered RAC arrangement (model C-III). Additionally, the experimental data is in good accord with the design of the double pass single duct solar air collector (model C). The experimental study shows that model C-III has a thermal efficiency of 60.2%, which is superior than model C-II's 53.1% and model C-I's 49.4%.

Sachin Kumar Bauri et al. (2021) In this study, a solar air heater with an artificial roughened surface was examined using computational fluid dynamics (CFD). The heater was equipped with 'S' shaped ribs above the collection plate. The primary goal is to improve the rate of heat transfer, followed by turbulence, by adding artificial protrusions to the surface of the absorber plate. The development of 'S' shaped ribs as a geometry on Nusselt number, friction factor, and performance enhancement has been completed for the relevant Reynolds number, which ranges from 6000 to 18000. Various types of turbulent models have been employed to address the issue, and the outcomes are subsequently compared to the Dittus-Boelter equation. The results of the Renormalization-group (RNG) $k-\epsilon$ model have been found to be in good agreement with the Dittus-Boelter equation. Therefore, this model is used to forecast heat transfer and friction factor in the duct. It has been noted that the highest thermo-hydraulic performance ratio is 1.48 at a specific Reynolds number when there is a uniform heat flow of 1000 W/m².

According to Sanjay Kumar Patel et al. (2020), the solar air heater is a significant type of solar heat collector. It can be utilised as a sub-system in various systems that are designed to use solar energy. Solar air heaters can be used for a variety of purposes, including drying or curing agricultural products, heating spaces for comfort, regenerating dehumidifying agents, seasoning lumber, and curing industrial products such as plastics. The design of a heater becomes complicated and expensive when it needs to produce high-temperature air. The solar air heater is the most reasonable option when it comes to the final use of heating air in order to keep the atmosphere at a comfortable temperature. In general, solar heaters are a good option for low and moderate temperatures because they have a simple design. The heat transmission efficiency of these solar air heaters is modest, but it can be enhanced by making geometrical adjustments, such as optimising duct shape or adding artificial roughness. Adding artificial roughness to the bottom of the absorber plate is a cost-effective and efficient method for enhancing the thermal

performance of a solar air heater. In order to enhance the transfer of heat from the absorber plate to the air that flows via solar air heaters, a number of experimental studies have been conducted using various types of roughness components. This research presents a computational fluid dynamics (CFD) investigation of heat transmission and friction in rectangular ducts that have been roughened with broken 'S' shaped ribs. The relative gap width (g/e) is 1.0, the relative gap position (d/W) varies from 0.30 to 0.60, and the other parameters remain unchanged. The impact of relative gap position (d/W) on the Nusselt number, friction factor, and thermo-hydraulic performance parameter has been analysed, and the results have been compared to those of a smooth duct under similar conditions. It has been determined that the highest heat transmission and friction characteristic occurs at a relative gap position of 0.50.

According to Mr. Akash Soni et al. (2019), solar air heaters are primarily utilised to transform renewable solar energy into useable energy. Solar heaters are primarily used to heat air and water. Various designs have been developed to improve the passage of heat from the heater. The primary goal of this effort is to improve the performance of a natural convection solar air heater. The CFD analysis of the convex shape solar air heater was performed, and the Nusselt number was calculated for different heat fluxes. In addition, it takes into account the impact of using ribs within the convex form solar heater and optimises the pitch between two fins in order to enhance the flow of heat from the duct.

According to Ali S. Hussien et al. (2020), modelling approaches are essential for predicting how well a solar air heater will function. Previous studies have shown that flat plate solar collectors with and without jet impingement led to a considerable improvement in performance. This work discusses the evaluation of thermal efficiency based on Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) in order to estimate the heat transfer characteristics of a solar air heater with and without jet impingement on a collector plate. The proposed design is modelled using Autodesk Inventor Professional, and computational fluid dynamics (CFD) software is utilised to simulate fluid flow and heat transfer. The design parameters that were taken into account in the work include solar collectors with and without jet impingement, jet diameters of 6, 8, and 10 mm for jet impingement, an ambient temperature of 300 K, a mass flow rate of 0.02 to 0.05 kg/s, and solar radiation of 500 to 800 W/m². The simulation results show that when the jet diameter is 6 mm, the collector outlet temperature, Nusselt number, and thermal efficiency are all higher at a mass flow rate of 0.05 and a solar radiation of 600 W/m². However, when the jet diameter is less than 6 mm, there is a pressure drop, which increases the amount of power the pump uses. The V-corrugated collector without a jet plate has a maximum efficiency of 64.3%, whereas the one with a jet plate has a maximum efficiency of 72.3%. Using jet impingement on the corrugated plate results in an improvement in thermal efficiency. The results obtained have been confirmed by comparing them with experimental data from the literature.

According to Inderjeet Singh et al. (2019), the lower thermal performance of conventional solar air heaters (SAH) can be improved by adding small-sized roughness features to the air-flow side of the absorber plate. This article describes the findings of a comparative study that investigated two new rib arrangements: multiple broken transverse ribs and square

wave-shaped ribs. The goal of the study was to improve performance in SAHs. The investigation includes rib characteristics such as $P/e = 10$, $e/D = 0.043$, and $W/w = 7$ for both arrangements. It is also explored at six levels of Reynolds number, which vary from 3000 to 18,000. An experimental and numerical examination has been conducted to study the impact of two different types of multiple-shaped ribs on heat transfer and friction factor features. The best parameters have been determined based on the performance of the thermo-hydraulic system. The CFD methodology has been confirmed to work for both the smooth and roughened duct. Square wave-shaped ribs provide a maximum thermal improvement of 2.50 times, but they also come with a pumping power penalty of 3.92 times. In contrast, many fractured ribs provide enhancements of 3.24 and 3.85 times, respectively. The experimental results are shown and explained through the visualisation of flow patterns and the contours of temperature, pressure, and turbulence.

The present simulation work of P. J. Bezbaruah et al. (2019) is based on a qualitative and quantitative examination of the thermohydraulic effect on a solar air heater that is caused by a unique shape of repeating rib. This shape is comparable to the shape of Miller teeth over the absorber plate. The overall efficiency is determined by measuring the thermohydraulic performance factor at different operating parameters, which takes into account both thermal and hydraulic performances. Using ANSYS FLUENT (version 18.1), a numerical simulation is performed with the Reynolds number changing from 3800 to 18000. The relative pitch ratio (P/e) is kept between 7.14 and 35.7, while the relative roughness height (e/D) is kept between 0.021 and 0.042. The impact of varying roughness heights and roughness pitches of miller teeth-shaped ribs on the heat transfer and fluid flow properties of a solar air collector is examined. A thorough rationale is provided utilising several shapes that were produced.

An experimental investigation was conducted by Vijayakumar Rajendran et al. (2021) to improve the performance of a solar air heater by adding artificial roughness to the absorber plate using baffles. This article examines the thermal and energy matrices of a Solar Air Heater (SAH) that has been roughened with V-up perforated baffles. The impact of different mass flow speeds on the SAH was examined with and without baffles. In order to verify the improvement in performance, the experimental outputs were assessed, including outlet air temperature, usable energy (heat) gain, and thermal efficiency. The baffled absorber plate SAH was found to have the highest thermal efficiency and useful energy gain of 89.3% and 1321.37W at a mass flow rate of 0.0346 kg/s, which is 13% and 12% higher than the SAH without a baffle. The V up-shaped ribs in flow arrangement provided superior thermal performance than smooth plate SAH for the parameter that was tested, according to the results. The analysis of the SAH system included an examination of energy matrices and a reduction of carbon dioxide emissions.

Arun Shrivastava et al. (2020) conducted a study on heat transmission and fluid flow processes in a solar air heater that was artificially roughened. The study used computational fluid dynamics (CFD). The impact of small diameter on the roughness of circular and square transverse wire ribs on heat transmission and fluid flow has been studied. The Reynolds number, relative roughness pitch (P/e), and relative roughness height (e/D) are used as design variables. The ANSYS

FLUENT 14.5 code is used to do a 3-D CFD simulation. The Renormalization-group (RNG) $k-\epsilon$ model is chosen as the best option. The results are confirmed by comparing them to the experimental results that are available. It is clear that the turbulence caused by the tiny width of the transverse wire ribs leads to a larger increase in heat transmission across the duct. On the other hand, using manufactured roughness leads to an increase in friction losses. The current computational fluid dynamics (CFD) analysis clearly shows that as the relative roughness height increases, the average Nusselt number and average friction factor also rise. The requirement for optimum performance has been defined in terms of a thermal enhancement factor of 1.39. The maximum value of the heat transfer coefficient that was discovered for the range of parameters that were tested is 31.6467.

Ajay Jain et al. (2018) conducted a three-dimensional computational fluid dynamics (CFD) analysis of a solar air heater to investigate the transmission of heat and the behaviour of fluid flow in a rectangular duct of a solar air heater. The duct had one roughened wall with a combination of circular and square transverse wire rib roughness. The heat transfer coefficient and friction factor have been researched in relation to the Reynolds number, roughness height, roughness pitch, relative roughness pitch, and relative roughness height. To confirm that the current numerical model is accurate, the findings have been compared to the experimental results that are available under similar flow circumstances. CFD investigation has been conducted in a medium Reynolds number flow. As the Reynolds number grows, the average Nusselt number also increases. The average Nusselt number reaches its highest value of 128.9646 when the relative roughness pitch is 20mm, the relative roughness height is 0.06mm, and the Reynolds number is 14000.

Nguyen Minh Phu et al. (2020) In this study, the authors reviewed energy and exergy studies of eleven roughness elements in solar air heater ducts. The effects of different roughness geometries, including ribs, twisted taps, baffles, and metal waste, on heat transfer and friction were investigated while air flowed over the absorber plate. The evaluation criteria for the roughness elements on the absorber plate were provided and compared. These criteria included the thermohydraulic performance parameters, thermal efficiency, effective efficiency, and exergy efficiency. The results indicated that the Nusselt number was highest when the ribs were projecting in an arc form. The ribs had the best thermohydraulic performance metrics when the Reynolds number was above 5000. The smallest exergy efficiencies were reported when jet impingement was used with arc-shaped ribs and roughness features in metal waste. The maximum effective and exergy efficiencies were 70% and 1.9%, respectively. The thermohydraulic performance parameter ranged from 0.5 to 2.0. This review work seeks to provide information about roughness geometries by examining both the first and second laws of thermodynamics and the figure of merits to characterise artificial roughness in a solar air heater.

Hwi-Ung Choi et al. (2020) In this study, a two-dimensional computational fluid dynamics (CFD) analysis was undertaken to explore the heat-transfer and fluid-friction properties of a solar air heater that has a transverse triangular

block at the bottom of the air duct. The design parameters that were selected include the Reynolds number, block height (ϵ), pitch (P), and length (l). The results are confirmed by comparing the Nusselt number predicted by the simulation with the experimental values that are available. The Renormalization-group (RNG) $k-\epsilon$ model with improved wall treatment was chosen as the best turbulence model. The results showed that the presence of a transverse triangular block provides a greater Nusselt number than that of a smooth air duct. The improvement in Nusselt number ranged from 1.19 to 3.37, depending on the geometric conditions that were studied. On the other hand, using a transverse triangular block also leads to a large increase in friction losses. The thermohydraulic performance (THPP) was also evaluated, with a maximum value of 1.001 at a Reynolds number of 8000. This maximum value occurs when the height (ϵ) is 20 mm, the length (l) is 120 mm, and the pitch (P) is 150 mm. In addition, the current study developed correlations of the Nusselt number and friction factor as a function of the geometrical conditions of the transverse triangular block and Reynolds number. These correlations can be used to predict the values of the Nusselt number and friction factor with absolute percentage deviations of 3.29% and 7.92%, respectively.

According to Mayank Sharma et al. (2021), solar energy plays a major role in the total increase in sustainable energy. Solar air heaters are used to take advantage of this strength since they are inexpensive and are commonly used as collector machines in many programs at low and moderate temperatures. Although many sun warmers were developed in the past, the main problem identified in its construction is the insufficient thermal strength, which was not applied properly. This is mostly due to the fact that the absorber plate's coefficient does not transfer heat well. Using computational fluid dynamics (CFD), the heat switch fee could be raised by adding synthetic roughness to the solar heater's absorber plate, and their effectiveness could be improved through simulations. By adding an absorber plate to the duct of the air heater, the temperature of the air intake and exhaust increases, which leads to higher temperature levels in solar heaters.

III. Gaps In Literature

The previous section's literature review has identified the following gaps in the research:

- To improve the performance of SAH, many types of roughness geometries have been examined and tested, including transverse rib, wingleet, arc ribs, and broken arc ribs with staggered ribs. There is no information in the literature about the usage of sinusoidal-shaped roughness in SAH.
- In order to evaluate the performance of roughened SAH, both analytical and experimental studies must be conducted on SAH with varied shapes of roughness.

IV. Conclusions

The current analysis has come to the following results on solar air heaters:

- Using computational fluid dynamics (CFD), the heat switch cost could be enhanced by adding synthetic roughness to the solar heater's absorber plate, and their effectiveness could be improved through simulations. The insertion of an absorber plate in the duct of an air heater increases the temperature of the air intake and exhaust, resulting in higher temperature levels for sun heaters.
- A transverse triangular block results in a greater Nusselt number than a smooth air duct. The improvement in Nusselt number ranged from 1.19 to 3.37, depending on the geometric conditions that were studied.
- The maximum Nusselt number was achieved with protruding ribs that were shaped like an arc. The ribs had the best thermohydraulic performance metrics when the Reynolds number was above 5000.
- The turbulence that is caused by the tiny diameter of the transverse wire ribs leads to a larger increase in heat transfer throughout the duct. On the other hand, using manufactured roughness leads to an increase in friction losses.
- This setup is a superior alternative for improving the performance of the solar air heater.
- When compared to the base model without corrugations, an arc-shaped corrugated absorber plate has superior heat transfer properties at all mass flow rates. On the other hand, the V-shaped corrugated absorber plate is more effective at transferring heat at greater mass flow rates, while the sine wave corrugated absorber plate is more successful at transferring heat at lower mass flow rates.

V. References

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